

***International Collaboration
Reinforcing Report***

Deliverable 2.6

Month 50 (October 2025)

Table of contents

General project information	3
Project partners	3
Introduction	4
1. Synergy with other projects on animal- microbiota interactions	4
HoloFood	4
SIMBA	4
EcoGen cluster (HoloRuminant - joint dissemination network)	5
Applied Hologenomics Conferences	5
Food 2030	6
Finding Pheno	6
CIRCLES	6
Earth Hologenome Initiative	7
2. Synergy with the European Microbiome Cluster	7
MicrobiomeSupport / SFSN	7
3. Synergy with other international projects that are relevant for 3D'omics	8
MSCA Doctoral Network "HoloGen"	8
Alternatives to Veterinary ANTimicrobials (AVANT)	8
Summary	9

General project information

Title	Three-dimensional holo'omic landscapes to unveil host-microbiota interactions shaping animal production
Acronym	3D'omics
Grant Agreement No.	101000309
Funding Programme	Horizon 2020
Instrument	RIA (Research and Innovation Action)
Project start date	01/09/2021
Duration of the project	52 months

Project partners

#	Partner	Abbrev	Type	Country
1	University of Copenhagen	UCPH	University	Denmark
2	Center for Genomic Regulation	CRG	Research Center	Spain
3	Veterinary University of Vienna	UVM	University	Austria
4	Max Delbrück Center	MDC	Research Center	Germany
5	KU Leuven	KUL	University	Belgium
6	ETH Zurich	ETH	University	Switzerland
7	Ben Gurion University	BGU	University	Israel
8	Norwegian University of Life Sciences	NMBU	University	Norway
9	Afekta Technologies Limited	ATL	Industry, SME	Finland
10	Aviagen, Inc.	AVI	Industry	United Kingdom
11	Novogene Netherlands B.V.	NGE	Industry	The Netherlands
12	Biomin, GmbH	BIO	Industry	Austria
13	Norsvin SA	NOR	Industry	Norway
14	Center for Genomic Analysis	CNAG	Research Center	Spain

Introduction

International Collaboration Reinforcing Plan (**Deliverable D2.2**) was submitted in month M12 of the project.

The International Collaboration Reinforcing Report was created by BGU, who was leading the coordination effort of 3D'omics with relevant international initiatives. There have been three different domains of collaborative interactions, namely for **synergy (1) with other projects on animal-microbiota interactions 3D'omics partners are involved in, then (2) with the so-called European Microbiome Cluster coordinated by MicrobiomeSupport, and also (3) with other international projects that are relevant for 3D'omics and vice versa**. This final Collaboration Reinforcing report includes the details of the networking and collaboration activities during the whole lifetime of the 3D' omics project. All other collaboration and outreach activities are reported on in more detail in **deliverable D2.4** ("Outreach and public engagement activity report").

1. Synergy with other projects on animal- microbiota interactions

HoloFood

HoloFood was a Horizon 2020 funded project (grant no 817729) that used a holistic approach to improve the efficiency of food production systems by deciphering the biomolecular and physiological processes triggered by incorporating feed additives and novel sustainable feeds in farmed animals. Although HoloFood ended in June 2023, the resulting resources are freely available and were used throughout the duration of 3D'omics.

Specifically, the poultry microbiome data generated in the project was employed for designing the experimental and sampling methodologies for the avian studies within 3D'omics. In addition, the bioinformatic pipelines, we developed for generation of multi-omic data, were also sourced from HoloFood. The 3D'omics database is also inspired by the HoloFood Data Portal (www.holofooddata.org), and employs a similar background engine for handling the database.

SIMBA

SIMBA (Sustainable Innovation of Microbiome Applications in the Food System) was also funded under the EU's Horizon 2020 Funding Programme (grant no 818431) and aimed at providing a holistic and innovative approach to the development of microbial solutions to increase food and nutrition security. SIMBA focused in particular on the identification of viable land and aquatic microbiomes. As SIMBA also ended in October 2023, the time for interactions

with this project was limited. However, the CM and PM attended the final conference of SIMBA in Copenhagen and used this opportunity to network closely with the organizers and attending stakeholders. The PM Antton Alberdi (UCPH) also participated in the panel discussion of the symposium.

EcoGen cluster (HoloRuminant - joint dissemination network)

3D'omics has joined a joint dissemination network of projects coordinated by the sister project HoloRuminant (Horizon 2020 funded, grant no 101000213), which had regular meetings throughout the duration of 3D'omics. The joint dissemination network consists of the five projects HoloRuminant, RUMIGEN, GEroNIMO, Re-Lifestock, and 3D'omics. The network provided an environment for these ongoing relevant European projects and international initiatives to optimize and share efforts, communication materials and resources. Relevant information has been shared with 3D'omics partners via email, during General Assemblies, and at conferences (e.g., Applied Hologenomic Conference). This network has organized several joint webinars, communicating project aims and findings to each other, but more importantly also to the interested general public and company stakeholders. These webinars were widely advertised on the 3D'omics and HoloRuminant social media channels. The network also applied for, and was awarded, an EU funded Horizon Results Booster grant (grant no. "HoloRuminant 101000213"), which resulted in the creation of the "EcoGen Cluster", several items of shared outreach material (i.e., flyers, explainer video, shared conference organizing material, and a joint policy brief) and the development of a shared Portfolio Dissemination Plan. The PM furthermore completed an EU offered moodle course on "Dissemination Capacity Building" in the framework of the Booster grant.

Applied Hologenomics Conferences

Several 3D'omics partners presented at the first Applied Hologenomics Conference in Bilbao in September 2022, where 3D'omics had a project poster, banner and stall for promotion, discussion, and networking. This conference has proven so fruitful and engaging for the partners and stakeholders, that 3D'omics co-organised the second Applied Hologenomics Conference 2024 (AHC2024) in Copenhagen in July 2024. The objective of the AHC2024 was to highlight key discoveries and novel approaches that aim at understanding the interactions of plant and animal hosts with their associated microbial communities, which could be directly or potentially applied into management and practice. This conference hosted over 200 international experts on the topic of Hologenomics. Three work package leaders and one advisory board member gave invited (keynote) talks at the conference and three posters on 3D'omic's results were presented, maximizing the exposure for 3D'omics. Furthermore, the conference provided excellent networking opportunities especially for junior researchers in the 3D'omics consortium.

Food 2030

The FOOD 2030 Online Platform was developed by the EU-funded project – CLEVERFOOD – as part of its efforts to organize a joined-up approach to transforming the food system for the benefit of the people and the planet. The platform is the home of two networks: the FOOD 2030 Project Collaboration Network and the FOOD 2030 Connected Lab Network. 3D'omics joined the Food 2030 Stakeholders mailing list and newsletter in 2021 and regularly received the updates, which were also disseminated via the 3D'omics social media channels to expand the 3D'omics network.

In December 2023, the European Commission organised a conference in Brussels entitled “Food 2030: green and resilient food systems” to showcase achievements of EU food systems related projects, explore future research and innovation orientations, and levers of change. 3D'omics coordinator Antton Alberdi (UCPH) gave a talk and participated in the panel discussion “Thinking out of the box”.

Finding Pheno

The H2020 project “FindingPheno” (grant no 952914) is focusing on the creation of a new computational framework for multi-omic data, and the generation of tools to better understand how host-microbiome interactions can affect growth, disease resistance, and more. Close communication with management of FindingPheno was ongoing throughout the project duration. The FindingPheno stakeholder synergy meeting in October 2021 (Copenhagen, Denmark) allowed for an excellent networking opportunity in early stages of 3D'omics. A shared outreach event (“Culture Night”) was organised in October 2023, with a joint booth and presentation of results. General cross-advertisement during outreach events was agreed upon.

Furthermore, ongoing discussions with FindingPheno partners from UCPH (Shyam Gopalakrishnan) and UTU (Leo Lahti) contributed significantly to the analytical procedures deployed in 3D'omics, including spatial microbiome analyses and mechanistic modelling approaches.

CIRCLES

CIRCLES is an EU H2020 project (grant no 818290), which aims to provide the scientific knowledge to exploit natural microbiomes for the sustainable production of high-quality food, with the ultimate objective to deliver new and healthier food applications. CIRCLES is exploring microbiome interactions and circulations across different food chains. PC Antton Alberdi (UCPH) went to the Circles Final Symposium (17.09.2024) in Brussels, Belgium. The event focused on food systems, environmental microbiomes and their application to improve productivity and quality in food chains. Specifically, Antton presented our research in a panel discussion about microbiome and circular strategies. The Circles final conference brought together renowned experts from over 14 European countries, as well as stakeholders from industry and policy, to network and discuss how microbiome research can improve food quality and productivity.

Earth Hologenome Initiative

PC Antton Alberdi (UCPH) coordinates this global initiative that aims at generating paired genomic and metagenomic data of wild organisms to research on ecology, evolution, and disease transmission. Merging data, knowledge, and connections developed during 3D'omics, a new research cluster was founded, led by NMBU (Norway) and UCPH (Denmark), with the participation of multiple international partners, including CIRAD (France) and IRTA (Spain). This group aims to connect the detailed host-microbiome knowledge generated during 3D'omics with insights the Earth Hologenome Initiative provides from wildlife research, to explore the detrimental effects of domestication and selection for intensive production in pigs.

2. Synergy with the European Microbiome Cluster

MicrobiomeSupport / SFSN

The MicrobiomeSupport Initiative established international networks of experts and stakeholders within the microbiome context. The coordinator, Angela Sessitsch, is also part of the 3D'omics advisory board. Although the MicrobiomeSupport Initiative officially ended in late 2022, the coordinators followed-up on the successful network by founding the MicrobiomeSupport Association. Therefore all the communication channels remained active, including Microbiomes4Life, the platform that links MicrobiomeSupport and R&D projects from the same cluster. Finally, the existing network has been transferred to a new platform (The Sustainable Food Systems Network - SFSN) and, in addition to 3D'omics being an active participant in this network, the PM has been a Microbiome ambassador since April 2023.

Over the lifetime of 3D'omics, several consortium members participated in the activities promoted and coordinated by Microbiome Support as well as participated in consortium actions such as conferences and meetings with other projects. PC Antton Alberdi was invited to give a talk on molecular studies of animal-microbiota interactions during the final conference of MicrobiomeSupport in Brussels in late June 2022. Furthermore, the Food System Microbiomes International Conference (May 2024, Torino, Italy) was organized as part of this newly founded MicrobiomeSupport Association at which PC Antton Alberdi also gave a talk.

3. Synergy with other international projects that are relevant for 3D'omics

MSCA Doctoral Network “HoloGen”

The MSCA Doctoral Network “HoloGen” (grant no 101169005; www.hologen-network.eu) was devised as an expansion programme of 3D'omics, a doctoral network action that would leverage the wealth of complementary data generated in 3D'omics to contribute to cutting-edge training of young researchers while making the most of the resources produced during 3D'omics. Launched in September 2024, the network encompasses 11 PhD students distributed across 6 European institutions. Two of the PhD students, hosted by the 3D'omics partners NMBU and Afekta, will employ data generated with swine and avian systems, respectively.

3D'omics was and will be introduced as a central asset for the network in the first two Training Retreats organised in Copenhagen (May 2025) and Barcelona (November 2025). Experimental setups, sampling schemes, laboratory procedures and bioinformatic pipelines implemented in 3D'omics were presented as model examples for high-quality generation and analysis of hologenomic datasets.

Alternatives to Veterinary ANTimicrobials (AVANT)

AVANT is a H2020 project (grant no 862829) aimed at developing alternatives to antimicrobials for the management of bacterial infections in pigs, especially diarrhea during the weaning period, as the major indication for antimicrobial use in livestock in Europe. PC Alberdi (UCPH) was in continuous communication with AVANT coordinator Luca Guardabassi, considering the possibility for joint actions during 3D'omics.

The collaboration with AVANT led to the implementation of molecular technologies developed in 3D'omics on respiratory microbiome and gut microbiome studies, yielding two manuscripts.

Pirolo M, Espinosa-Gongora C, **Alberdi A**, **Eisenhofer R**, Soverini M, Eriksen EO, Pedersen KS, Guardabassi L. 2023. Bacterial topography of the upper and lower respiratory tract in pigs. *Animal Microbiome* 5: 5. doi:10.1186/s42523-023-00226-y

Pirolo M, Sherwani MK, Espinosa-Gongora C, Eriksen EO, Tassinato C, **Alberdi A**, Guardabassi L. 2025. Faecal microbiome profiling uncovers biomarkers for piglets resilient to post-weaning diarrhoea. Under review.

Summary

In addition to the networking interactions listed above, 3D'omics also had a large number of international networking activities with industry stakeholders/companies that, for confidentiality reasons, cannot be disclosed in the public report that **deliverable D2.6** represents. Therefore, we report on these activities in the final technical report of 3D'omics.

Overall, 3D'omics successfully utilized and established new networks with a large number of international projects and other stakeholders within the duration of the project. Data and method sharing is a vital part of the project. We have archived the key results we have set out to accomplish in the International Collaboration Reinforcing plan (**deliverable D2.2**).

